

DETERMINING THE ROLE OF $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ EXCHANGER IN THE RELAXANT EFFECT OF VINCANINE HYDROCHLORIDE AND PYROZALINE IODIDE ALKALOIDS

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Abstract. *This study presents the results of research into the relaxant effects of alkaloids vincanine hydrochloride and pyroزالine iodide on receptor-operated Ca^{2+} channels in smooth muscle cells of the aorta. The isometric contractile activity of smooth muscle from rat aorta was studied using mechanography. In experiments examining $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange activity, the effects of the studied alkaloids on receptor-operated Ca^{2+} channels were confirmed by the use of α -adrenoreceptor blocker phentolamine (FA) (10 μM). In these experiments, the Na^+/K^+ -ATPase blocker ouabain (20 μM) was used to study $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange activity. Ouabain inhibits Na^+/K^+ -ATPase on the plasma membrane, which leads to a decrease in the concentration gradient of Na^+ and K^+ ions across the membrane, enhancing reverse $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange and allowing the influx of Ca^{2+} ions into smooth muscle cells. It was concluded that the blockade of receptor-operated Ca^{2+} channels might play a significant role in the relaxant effect of indole alkaloids.*

Keywords: *smooth muscle cell, aorta, ion channels, Na^+/K^+ -ATPase, vasorelaxant.*

Introduction. Smooth muscle cells (SMCs) of blood vessels play a key role not only in the physiological functions of blood vessels, such as vasoconstriction and vasodilation, but also in the pathogenesis of vascular diseases, particularly hypertension and atherosclerosis. The contraction and relaxation of vascular wall SMCs depend on the function of Ca^{2+} transport systems located in the plasma membrane and the sarcoplasmic reticulum membrane [5]. In vitro, vascular SMCs are typically stimulated to contract by using α -AR agonists like noradrenaline and phenylephrine [2]. Additionally, systems such as the purinergic system and the $\text{Na}^+/\text{K}^+/\text{2Cl}^-$ cotransporter (NKCC) are important in regulating the functional activity of vascular SMCs [3]. It has been noted that the concentration gradient of Na^+ and K^+ ions across the plasma membrane of vascular SMCs affects $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{in}}$ homeostasis by reversing the function of $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange [1]. In these studies, ouabain at a concentration of 1 μM was used as a Na^+/K^+ -ATPase blocker, and it has been shown that Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity can also be blocked in conditions where $[\text{K}^+]_{\text{out}} = 0 \text{ mM}$ [4].

The purpose of the study is to determine the role of receptor-operated (Ca^{2+}R) Ca^{2+} channels in providing the relaxant effect of vincanine hydrochloride and pyroزالine iodide alkaloids on smooth muscle cells (SMCs).

Research material and methods. The isometric contractile activity of rat aorta smooth muscle was recorded using the standard mechanography technique [6]. Experimental animals were euthanized by dislocation, the thorax was surgically opened, and the aorta was removed and cleaned of fatty tissues in a Petri dish filled with Krebs-Henseleit physiological solution. The aorta was cut into rings of ~3–4 mm in length and mounted in an experimental chamber (5 ml), one side

attached to a special hook and the other to an isometric force transducer, Grass FT-03 (Grass Instrument, USA).

The experimental chamber (5 ml) was continuously perfused with Krebs-Henseleit physiological solution from a special reservoir, with a constant temperature maintained by a thermostat. The solution was aerated with a gas mixture of 95% O₂ and 5% CO₂. The contractile activity of the aortic preparation was recorded using the Grass FT-03 mechanograph (Grass Instrument, USA) and amplified via a signal amplifier connected to the Endim 621.02 device (Czech Republic).

The Krebs-Henseleit solution in the experimental chamber had the following composition (in mM): NaCl – 118; KCl – 4,8; MgSO₄ – 1,2; KH₂PO₄ – 1,2; CaCl₂ – 2,5; NaHCO₃ – 25; glucose – 11 (pH = 7.4). The solution was aerated with a carbogen mixture (O₂ – 95% and CO₂ – 5%) and maintained at a constant temperature (t = 37 ± 0.5 °C) by a thermostat. Initially, the rat aortic preparation was incubated under a tension of 1 g = 9.8 mN for 45-60 minutes until steady electromotive activity was recorded.

The isometric contractile activity of the vascular smooth muscle preparation was automatically recorded by the Endim 621.02 (Czech Republic) device. Phenylephrine (1 μM), an α₁-adrenoreceptor (α₁-AR) agonist, was used to induce contraction in the aortic smooth muscle preparation under isometric conditions. In experiments investigating Na⁺/Ca²⁺ exchange activity, ouabain (20 μM) was used as a Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase blocker, and phentolamine (FA) (10 μM), an α-adrenoreceptor blocker, was used to confirm the effect of the studied alkaloids on receptor-operated Ca²⁺ channels.

In the experiments, vincanine hydrochloride, pyrovaline iodide, L-NAME (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany), NaHCO₃, CaCl₂, MgSO₄, glucose, NaCl, KCl, NaH₂PO₄ (Russia) reagents were used. The obtained results were statistically processed using Student's t-test.

Research results and their analysis. In experiments studying Na⁺/Ca²⁺ exchange activity, the effects of the alkaloids on receptor-operated Ca²⁺ channels were confirmed using the α-adrenoreceptor blocker phentolamine (FA) (10 μM). The Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase blocker ouabain (20 μM) was also used in these experiments to study Na⁺/Ca²⁺ exchange activity. The inhibition of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase by ouabain on the plasma membrane leads to a reduction in the concentration gradient of Na⁺ and K⁺ ions across the membrane, which in turn activates the reverse mode of Na⁺/Ca²⁺ exchange, allowing Ca²⁺ ions to enter smooth muscle cells.

It is well known that Na⁺/Ca²⁺ exchange plays an important role in the contraction activity of vascular smooth muscle cells controlled by α-adrenoreceptors on the plasma membrane. Under normal conditions, Na⁺/Ca²⁺ exchange functions bidirectionally, primarily expelling intracellular Ca²⁺ ions, which is crucial for maintaining intracellular balance and ensuring steady contraction activity in smooth muscle cells. Consequently, in subsequent experiments, the role of Na⁺/Ca²⁺ exchange in the relaxant effect of the indole alkaloids vincanine and pyrovaline iodide was investigated. For this purpose, the effect of these alkaloids on aortic contraction induced by Na⁺-free Krebs solution and ouabain, which promotes Ca²⁺ influx through Na⁺/Ca²⁺ exchange, was studied.

The results showed that vincanine and pyrovaline iodide alkaloids significantly reduced aortic contractions induced by Na⁺-free solution. The effects of vincanine and pyrovaline iodide were dose-dependent: at concentrations of 50 μM and 250 μM, they reduced aortic contraction by 25.3±4.5% and 39.1±4.2%, respectively, compared to the control (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The effect of vincanine and pyrovaline iodide on rat aorta contraction induced by Na^+ -free Krebs solution. The ordinate axis represents the contraction force of the aorta induced by Na^+ -free solution, taken as 100%. The abscissa shows the concentration of the alkaloids (in all cases, the significance level is indicated as $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$; $n = 4$).

These results suggest that the observed relaxant effects of the studied alkaloids are due to the inhibition of Ca^{2+} transport through $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange. To further investigate the regulation of the $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange system through modulation of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity in vascular smooth muscle cells, additional experiments were conducted. The effect of the alkaloids on Ca^{2+} ion transport via $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange was further confirmed in experiments using the cardiac glycoside ouabain (OU). As previously mentioned, under normal conditions, the $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange system functions to expel Ca^{2+} ions from the cell (normal mode). However, when $[\text{Na}^+]_{\text{in}}$ increases or $[\text{Na}^+]_{\text{out}}$ decreases, the $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange system operates in reverse mode, importing Ca^{2+} ions into the cell as Na^+ ions are extruded. This can occur under pathological conditions such as ischemia or when Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity, responsible for extruding Na^+ ions from the cell, is reduced.

Modulation of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity is believed to play a significant role in the pathogenesis of hypertension. In the experiments, it was noted that the reduction of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity led to an increase in the contraction strength of smooth muscle cells.

Cardiac glycosides (such as ouabain) have been found to increase the amplitude of contraction in smooth muscle cells, including those from rat vasculature. This increase is attributed to the inhibition of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase activity, which in turn raises the intracellular $[\text{Na}^+]_{\text{in}}$ concentration, leading to Ca^{2+} influx through the reverse mode of $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange, ultimately resulting in cell contraction. The inhibition of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase by ouabain on the plasma membrane decreases the concentration gradient of Na^+ and K^+ ions, facilitating Ca^{2+} influx into smooth muscle cells via $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange. Ouabain binds to the α -subunit of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase, reducing its activity, which increases $[\text{Na}^+]_{\text{in}}$ and enhances the reverse mode of $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange, leading to increased intracellular $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ and consequently, increased contraction strength.

In the next set of experiments, the effect of the alkaloids on ouabain-induced rat aorta contractions was studied (Figure 2). In these experiments, the contraction force of the aorta

induced by phenylephrine (1 μM) was taken as 100%, while ouabain (20 μM) induced a contraction force of $76.4 \pm 3.4\%$ of this value.

Further confirmation of the effects of the studied alkaloids on Ca^{2+} transport via $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange was obtained in experiments using the cardiac glycoside ouabain (OU). Ouabain causes contraction of the aorta through Ca^{2+} influx into smooth muscle cells via $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange. In our experiments, the indole alkaloids vincanine (50 μM) and pyroزالine iodide (250 μM) reduced ouabain-induced aortic contraction in a dose-dependent manner, with contractions reduced by $26.2 \pm 4.2\%$ and $32.3 \pm 4.6\%$, respectively, compared to the control (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The effect of vincanine and pyroزالine iodide alkaloids on rat aorta contraction induced by ouabain. The ordinate axis represents the contraction force induced by 20 μM ouabain, taken as 100%. The abscissa shows the concentration of the alkaloids (in all cases, the significance level is indicated as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$; $n = 4$).

The results suggest that, in addition to the blockade of voltage-dependent L-type Ca^{2+} channels and receptor-operated Ca^{2+} channels, the $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchanger in smooth muscle cells may also play a role in the relaxant effect of vincanine and pyroزالine iodide alkaloids.

Conclusion. Vincanine and pyroزالine iodide alkaloids reduce the contraction strength of aorta induced by Na^+ -free solution and ouabain with similar efficacy. This is evidenced by the close proximity of their half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) values. The similarity of the IC_{50} values obtained using two different activation methods of aorta contraction, primarily through Ca^{2+} influx via $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchange, strongly indicates that this mechanism is involved in their relaxant effect.

The results of these experiments suggest that, along with the blockade of voltage-dependent L-type Ca^{2+} channels and receptor-operated Ca^{2+} channels, the $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchanger in smooth muscle cells may also participate in the relaxant effect of these alkaloids.

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